

Study in Nitrogen Mustards. Part II : Synthesis of Some 2-Alkyl-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinone Derivatives as Possible Antitumour Agents

PRITPAL SINGH*

Department of Chemical Engineering and Technology, Panjab University,
Chandigarh-160 014, (India).

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Several mono- and bifunctional nitrogen mustards attached to aminoalkyl derivatives of some quinazolones, through a methylene group linkage have been synthesised, since the quinazolone nucleus was found to exert powerful activating influence on both the bis- and mono- nitrogen mustard moieties and studied for their antitumour action.

DIVERSE biological activities have been encountered in compounds having the quinazolinone ring system¹. For example, the quinazolinone alkaloids, febrifugin² and vasicinone³, are reputed to elicit antimalarial and bronchodilator activity, respectively. 4(3H)-quinazolinones with CNS activity⁴ are known and 2-methyl-3-*o*-tolyl-4(3H) quinazolinone (meth-aqualone)⁵ has been utilized in therapy as a hypnotic and sedative; 2-ethyl-6-sulphonamido-7-chloro-1,2-dihydro-4(3H)-quinazolinone (quinethazone)⁶ is a diuretic; other quinazolinones have been found to possess muscle relaxant,^{8,7} antiinflammatory,⁷ antimitotic⁸, antihistaminic⁹, and hypotensive activities¹⁰.

Numerous 4(3H)-quinazolinones, particularly those with 2-alkyl-3-aryl^{4,11} 2-alkyl-3-alkyl¹², and 2-alkyl-3-amino¹³ have been prepared and evaluated biologically. Peck *et al*¹⁴, synthesised a large number of heterocyclic compounds containing one or more nitrogen mustard groups, substituted directly or through the side chain, at different positions of the ring system, have shown good anticancer activity in various biological test systems. Creech *et al*¹⁵, screened a large number of compounds of acridine, quinoline, quinazolines and various other heterocyclic systems, containing nitrogen mustard moiety and have confirmed the idea that these compounds can be further modified or can be more efficiently used in various cancerous and leukemic diseases. Recently some work on 4(3H)-quinazolinone derivatives at Sloan-Kettering Institute for Cancer Research, New York, U. S. A. have shown that these compounds possess antileukemic activities¹⁶. From the earlier works it was evident that the exceptional antitumour activity of certain monofunctional nitrogen mustards was determined

by the chemical structure of the heterocyclic nucleus that was attached through a side chain to the mono-2-chloroethylamino group. The first half nitrogen mustard that displayed pronounced activity in prolonging the survival time of mice, bearing several varieties of ascities tumours were the derivatives of acridine¹⁶. On the other hand, the partial acridine structures with similar substitutions showed to no antitumour activity. Since their corresponding is mustards were highly effective, it is apparent that both the heterocyclic nucleus and the presence of an alkyl group are of critical importance (in enhancing the activity of monofunctional mustard grouping).

Considering all these factors it was thought of interest to study whether the presence of an additional aryl or alkyl group on the quinazolinone nucleus, through which the mustard group is attached, could play a significant role in this activation and whether any modification of simple heterocyclic nuclei would impart enhanced physiological activity to the mustard moiety. The presence of a mustard moiety at position 3, attached through the side chain, of the variously substituted quinazolones, as well as the presence of an alkyl substituent at position 2, were investigated both in mono- and the bis- form of the mustard moiety, as shown in Table 1 and 2.

Three different methods were employed to synthesise these derivatives, in order to confirm their structures. Various substituted amines used for condensation reactions of the different compounds of Table 1 are reported in our previous paper¹⁷. Amines for the compounds of Table 2 were prepared according to the method of Ishidate *et al*¹⁸, Benn *et al*¹⁹, Tsou *et al*²⁰, and Hebborn *et al*²¹. The compounds were either prepared by condensing equimolar quantities of N-formly or

*Present Address : Organic Chemistry Laboratories,
University of Technology, Loughborough,
Leics, LE II, 3TU.

N-acetyl derivatives of anthranilic acid with the substituted aryl or alkyl amines (Scheme 1) in the presence of phosphorous trichloride in dry toluene according to the method of Grimmel *et al*²², Mewada *et al*²⁸, or Okumura *et al*²⁴.

Scheme-1

Some of these compounds were prepared by fusing substituted acetantranils with equivalent amount of appropriate arylamines (Scheme-2) according to the method of Zentmeyer and Wagner²⁵ or Jain and Narang²⁶. The required acetantranils were prepared by refluxing the corresponding N-acetyl anthranilic acid with excess of acetic anhydride. The various compounds are reported in Table 1 and 2.

Scheme-2

Another group of compounds were prepared by fusing 2-alkyl-3 : 1 : 4-benzoxazones with corresponding monoethanolamine and the resulting product was chlorinated by using thionyl chloride as chlorinating agent. The halogenated products were further condensed with the appropriate amines to get the desired product (Scheme-3). The various compounds are reported in Table 3.

Scheme-3

The structures of these compounds, crystallised either from ethanol or methanol, were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, i.e. spectroscopy and chemical studies. The newly synthesised compounds are now being screened for their pharmacological evaluation. Most of the compounds have shown presumptive activity against lymphoid leukemia L1210 in their preliminary screening. A full length paper on their structure activity relationship is appearing shortly.

Experimental

All m. ps were determined by using Gallen-Kamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

2-Methyl-3 [3'-N, N-bis (2-chloroethyl) aminomethyl-4'-ethoxy] Phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (Table 1 and 3).

Method A : 3'-N, N-Bis (2-chloroethyl) aminomethyl-4'-ethoxy aniline (2.91 g., 0.01 mole) and 2-methyl-3 : 1 : 4-benzoxazine (2.4 g., 0.01 mole) were condensed together by heating first at low flame and then at 160-170° for 4 to 5 hr. on an oil bath. The reaction mixture was cooled, triturated with 10 ml. ethylalcohol at 0° and filtered. The product was crystallised from methyl alcohol colourless needles (3.9 g., 75%), m.p. 207-209°.

Method B : 3'-N,N-Bis(2-chloroethyl) aminomethyl-4'-ethoxy aniline (2.91 g., 0.01 mole) was added to a solution of methyl-N-acetyl-anthranilate (1.93 g., 0.01 mole) in dry toluene (125 ml). Phosphorous trichloride (3 ml. in 12 ml. toluene) was then added dropwise to the mixture with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. Excess of toluene was then distilled off and the last traces were removed under reduced pressure. The residual mass was triturated with weak alkali solution (5%). The precipitated base was filtered and crystallised from the suitable solvent.

Similarly various other 2-substituted-3 [3'-N-mono or N, N-bis (2-haloethyl) aminomethyl-4'-alkoxy] phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones were prepared by either method as reported in Table 1.

Method C : 3 N or N, N-bis (2-hydroxyethyl) aminomethyl-4-alkoxy anilines were condensed together with equimolar amounts of 2-alkyl-3 : 1 : 4-benzoxazines by the usual method as explained in Method A, to get 2-alkyl-3 [3'-N or N, N-bis (2-hydroxyethyl) aminomethyl-4'-alkoxy] phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone.

2-Alkyl-3 [3'-N or N, N-bis (2-chloroethyl) aminomethyl-4'-alkoxy] Phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones [Table 2] :

2-Alkyl-3[3'-N or N, N-bis (2-hydroxyethyl) aminomethyl-4'-alkoxy] phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones (0.01 mole) dissolved in dry chloroform were transferred to a well stirred solution of thionyl chloride (30 ml.) in dry chloroform with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for half an hour on a steam bath, excess of chloroform and thionyl chloride (if any) was removed under reduced pressure. The solid residual mass obtained was crystallised as mono-or dihydrochloride.

The base was obtained by treating the hydrochloride with mild alkali solution.

TABLE—1

No.	R ¹	R	X	Y	Mol. formula	M. P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen (%)	
								Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	H	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	252-254	58	10.25	10.34
2.	CH ₃	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	229-231	63	9.88	10.00
3.	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	207-209	75	9.57	9.67
4.	CH ₃	H	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	281-282	47	8.35	8.48
5.	CH ₃	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	271-272	47	8.14	8.25
6.	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	267-269	50	7.91	8.03
7.	CH ₃	H	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ BrCl	279-280	55	9.17	9.32
8.	CH ₃	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ BrCl	247-248	46	8.67	9.00
9.	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂ BrCl	225-227	56	8.58	8.77
10.	CH ₃	H	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-H	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	261-262	50	12.15	12.22
11.	CH ₃	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-H	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	250-251	55	11.63	11.74
12.	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-H	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	227-229	57	11.18	11.30
13.	CH ₃	H	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-H	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ Br	282-283	62	10.69	10.82
14.	CH ₃	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-H	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Br	264-265	67	10.34	10.45
15.	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-H	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₂ Br	259-260	67	10.00	10.09
16.	H	H	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	248-249	60	10.61	10.71
17.	H	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	221-222	67	10.21	10.34
18.	H	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	214-215	46	9.77	10.00
19.	H	H	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	300	52	8.60	8.73
20.	H	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	279-280	60	8.37	8.48
21.	H	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	271-272	60	8.18	8.25
22.	H	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ BrCl	229-230	61	9.54	0.62
23.	H	CH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-H	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ Cl	266-267	60	9.23	9.32
24.	H	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	-H	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	261-262	69	8.89	9.04
25.	H	C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ CH ₂ Br	-H	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ Br	251-252	64	10.37	10.45

Additional analyses were also performed for compound 2, 3, 9, 12, 22 (C, H) ; 6, 14(Br) and 18(Cl) and the results within $\pm 0.4\%$ of their calculated values.

TABLE—2

No.	R ¹	Z	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield	Nitrogen (%)	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ (-p)	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂ S	130-132	75	9.38	9.54
2.	CH ₃	-SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ (-p)	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂ S	136-137	58	9.35	9.54
3.	H	-SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ (-p)	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂ S	142-143	51	9.57	9.86
4.	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	128-130	70	15.86	15.97
5.	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ .2HCl	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O.Cl ₄	237-239	80	11.11	11.26
6.	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O.Br ₂	260 (d)	73	10.67	10.80
7.	H	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ .HCl	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₃ O.Cl ₃	212-214	85	13.60	13.68
8.	CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ (-p)	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O.Cl ₂	187-188	60	11.08	11.17
9.	H	-C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ (-p)	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O.Cl ₂	204-205	56	11.49	11.60

Additional analyses were also performed for compounds 2, 4(C, H) ; 3(Cl) and 6 (Br) and the results were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of their calculated values.

2-Alkyl-3'-N or N, N-bis(2-bromoethyl) aminoethyl-4'-alkoxy] phenyl-4(3)-quinazolinone :

lumps obtained were crystallised from the suitable solvents.

3-Hydroxyethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone [Table 3] :

2-Alkyl-3 [3'-N or N,N-bis (2-bromoethyl) aminoethyl-4'-alkoxy] phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones (0.01 mole) were heated with phosphorous tribromide (3.2 mole) on an oil bath for 3-4 hr. It was cooled and poured over crushed ice. The solid

3-Hydroxyethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (12.5 g., 0.06 mole) dissolved in dry chloroform (30 ml) was treated with thionyl chloride (35 ml) in chloroform by the usual method. The base was crystallised from ethyl alcohol (80%) into white needles (67%), m.p. 184-185°.

TABLE—3

No.	R ¹	R	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen (%)	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ OH) ₂	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃	174-175	82	14.28	14.43
2.	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ O.Cl ₂	178-179	76	12.57	12.80
3.	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ O.Br ₂	206-207	80	9.95	10.07
4.	H	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O.Cl ₂	174-175	65	13.19	13.37
5.	H	-N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Br) ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O.Br ₂	216-217	66	10.26	10.42
6.	CH ₃	-NH.C ₆ H ₅ (OC ₂ H ₅).CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	226-227	46	11.46	11.74
7.	CH ₃	-NH.C ₆ H ₅ (OCH ₃).CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	210-211	50	11.92	12.09
8.	CH ₃	-NH.C ₆ H ₅ (OH).CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	220-221	54	12.31	12.47
9.	CH ₃	-NH.N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O.Cl ₂	231-232	70	16.16	16.32
10.	H	-NH.N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O.Cl ₂	241-242	60	16.82	17.02
11.	H	-NH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂ (-p)	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	126-127	66	11.87	11.94
12.	H	-NH.C ₆ H ₅ (OC ₂ H ₅).CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₂ Cl) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	232-233	50	13.40	12.08
13.	CH ₃	-NH.C ₆ H ₅ (OC ₂ H ₅).CH ₂ NHCH ₂ CH ₂ Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	196-197	50	13.40	13.51

Additional analyses were also performed for compounds 4, 8, 13(C,H) and 3, 6, 13 (Cl) and the results were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of their calculated values.

2-Methyl-3-hydroxyethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone [Table 3]

2-Methyl-3 : 1 : 4-benzoxazone (16.1 g., 0.1 mole) was fused with mono-ethylamine (6.1 g., 0.1 mole) at 140-160° by the usual method as explained. The solid was crystallised from methanol ethyl acetate mixture into cream coloured lumps (52%, m.p. 182-183°).

2-Methyl-3-chloroethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone [Table 3] :

2-Methyl-3-hydroxyethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (7.0 g., 0.03 mole) dissolved in dry chloroform (20 ml.) was treated with thionyl chloride (18 ml) in dry chloroform by the usual method. The base was crystallised from ethyl alcohol m.p. 163-164°.

2-Alkyl-3[(substituted) aminoethyl] 4(3H)-quinazolinones :

A mixture of 2-alkyl-3-chloroethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (0.01 mole) and the substituted amine (0.01 mole) in equimolar ratio were refluxed together in ethyl alcohol for 4-5 hr. Excess of alcohol was removed by distillation and the residual mass treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid mass obtained was crystallised from suitable solvents. The free hydroxyl-group was further halogenated using halogenating agent.

The various compounds prepared are reported in Table 3.

The different compounds reported in Table 2 were similarly prepared by condensing the appropriate substituents.

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